

Cyber Security in Higher Education: Problem and Solution

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Abstract: *Cyber security has emerged as a critical concern in today's digital age, affecting various sectors and industries worldwide. Among these, higher education institutions have become prime targets for cyber-attacks and other security threats due to the vast amount of valuable and sensitive information they possess. These institutions house a wealth of personal, financial, and research data, making them attractive targets for malicious actors seeking to exploit vulnerabilities in their information systems. These threats may lead to reputational damage, financial losses, and even legal repercussions. Moreover, the disruption caused by such attacks can significantly hinder the academic and administrative functions of these institutions, affecting students, faculty, and staff alike. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of the problem of cyber security in higher education and offer viable solutions to address these issues. To achieve this objective, a thorough review of existing literature related to cyber security in higher education will be conducted. This review will delve into the various types of cyber threats faced by these institutions with a focus on the problems and their solutions. By highlighting the pressing nature of cyber security challenges in higher education and providing practical solutions, this paper endeavours to equip institutions with the knowledge and awareness of the current situation of the cyber threats. It is essential for higher education institutions to proactively address these issues to safeguard their reputation, maintain the trust of stakeholders, and ensure the continuity of their educational goals.*

Keywords: Information Security; Cyber Security; Higher Education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet is now a fundamental component of many people's daily lives. Users engage in a variety of activities involving their private data over the Internet daily. These activities include Internet banking, educational services, medical care, and e-commerce. According to Nazahah et al. (2020), higher education is one of the industries facing risks. There have been cases of institutions being subjected to cyber-attacks in which information was stolen. Users in higher education institutions rely on gadgets that allow them to be highly flexible. This has made it easier for them to adapt to the Internet and access it at any time and from any gadget. However, ensuring cybersecurity in higher education institutions is incredibly challenging.

According to Aruna (2017), Malaysia is highly associated with cybersecurity and is ranked third out of 193 countries. In 2017, there were 6,274 reported cyber-attack incidents. This demonstrates that the internet is not completely protected. Thus, awareness about cybersecurity is critical given the increasing dependency on computer systems and the internet. With several incidents recorded, higher

education institutions have become common targets for cybercriminals (Rohan et al., 2023). These institutions keep and manage an enormous amount of vital research data, sensitive personal information of students, lecturers, and non-academic staff members, as well as teaching and academic information. As a result, hackers are interested in violating educational institutions, which could result in consequences such as intellectual property loss, reputation damage, economic costs, and disruption of education. According to Chabrow (2015), inadequate cybersecurity puts higher education at risk, and the abundance of academic research information has made educational institutions an appealing target for cybercriminals. This is concerning for the higher education industry, as cyber risks such as hacking can potentially interrupt academic operations. Hackers use the important details obtained from institutions and can effortlessly market the data because data has become an asset. Institutions' online systems are a potential subject of cybersecurity concerns.

Almost every activity in higher education institutions relies mainly on computer technology and internet access. Higher education systems are closely linked to the Internet world. However, cyberspace is dangerous due to theft and illegal behaviour, which results in cyber security issues. Cyber security protects computer-related systems, such as hardware, software, and digital information, from theft, destruction, interruption, or fraud (Nazahah et al., 2020).

The work presented here focuses on cybersecurity issues in higher education institutions and suggests solutions that can be utilized to address these issues. With this information, organizations can be well-informed and provided with targeted assistance to avoid falling victim to cyber threats.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This paper provides a brief review of the existing literature on cyber security in higher education, with a particular emphasis on the problem and its solution. The study was carried out to determine the source of the problem as well as the best solution to address information security. Higher education circles and discussion groups have been used to provide insights into the current undergraduate situation.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 *Cyber Security Problems in Higher Education*

3.1.1 *Weak security system policy that affects cyber security*

Among the cyber security problems in institutions of higher education include having a weak security system policy that affects cyber security. According to a report by BitSight (a cyber risk management company) higher education has the highest rate of ransomware attacks among all industries studied. Huge financial losses, due to ransomware attacks or data breaches (Noran Shafik Fouad, 2021). Ransomware virus is a virus or malware that can access all the data in the victim's laptop while the victim will not be able to access the data in his laptop until the money requested by the spreader is paid. According to (Eva D. Kundy and Benson James Lyimo, 2019) the impact of this vulnerability often comes from anyone who has access to IT-related networks or systems such as employees and vendors. According to (Hoog 2015) vendors often place and introduce unsafe products in the market thus creating risks. This problem is often labeled as 'technical security debt'. If the products sold in the market are used by most high institutions, the risk of this cyber threat will increase. Furthermore, those in charge of information system management in higher education institutions were found to be unconcerned about updating software and operating systems that would significantly

improve their higher education institutions' security posture and reduce potential risks. (Dr. Joanna ywytkowska, 2022). The risk of being attacked by a virus is very high if the system is not updated regularly. Hackers rely on known vulnerabilities since 2002 and there are almost 90% of recorded cases (Harrison, Pagliery 2015).

Furthermore, untrained workers and staff invite direct access attacks in large organizations, including school and university liaisons (George B. Liluashvili). One of the issues found in weak security system policies is untrained staff and workers. If the issues of worker skill shortages and job mismatches are not addressed, they can significantly increase cyber threats. This also happens because of the lack of support from top management, staff, and management security awareness of cyber security Alfawaz (2015). The superiors are not sensitive to the weaknesses of the security system implemented in institutions of higher learning, thus inviting various cyber threats that can damage the existing system. Among the attacks experienced in the case of weak security system policy include the risk of phishing attacks. According to (Christopher & Michele, 2015) phishing is a digital crime that targets the victim's sensitive information or data through email, social media uploads, or text messages. Arguably, phishing activities aim to entice people to voluntarily provide personal information unwittingly for criminal purposes. Not only that, having a weak security system will also cause higher education institutions to experience malware attacks. Malware can be defined as harmful software capable of interfering with or manipulating the normal operation of digital devices (Eric CK Cheng and Tianchong Wang, 2022). Malware can remain in the system for long periods without the knowledge of the system owner. These attacks often occur due to human error or lack of vigilance. From the attack the institution will receive various negative effects. Among them it will damage the good name of the company. The information system is affected if the system is damaged. Even if the system continues to work, it still needs to be implemented. This situation caused the reputation of the company to be damaged. The information system will be greatly affected if the system breaks down in a high-risk group. Almost half the system became unusable. For the system to work, it must be replaced. This situation affects the reputation of the company.

3.1.2 Cyber threats caused by the human factor

When developing human knowledge to protect society from technical attacks, a major pitfall and ongoing issue confronts higher education institutions. Despite modern cyber security preparedness and trained personnel, hacking activities flourish with malicious actions aimed at stealing critical sensitive information from higher education institutions. Furthermore, environmental, social, political, constitutional, organizational, economic, and personal factors influence the user's ability to detect and mitigate identified threats. According to the research, employees who are at risk of hacking must be classified after analyzing the challenges of traditional and modern tools and developing training programs to ensure that hacker actions are unsuccessful. Furthermore, eliminating social engineering breaches is nearly impossible unless efforts are made to raise the level of information security awareness among all employees to address the cyber security risks posed by students at higher education institutions. According to researchers, a person's email address will remain an online identity despite the many modern applications for communication. The purpose of the study is to identify security vulnerabilities in email. This allows malicious actors to engage in phishing via phishing emails.

The shortage of cybersecurity professionals will continue to be a major challenge for higher education institutions (the ISACA State of Cybersecurity 2020 report), with little progress to report (ISACA, 2020) to institutions of higher education (Burrell, 2020; Crumpler & Lewis, 2019). ISACA's Global State of Cybersecurity Study, which surveyed 2,000 above cybersecurity professionals across 17 industries, found:

- 62% stated that their cybersecurity team lacked manpower.

- 57% reported that they had not yet recruited for cybersecurity positions.
- 70% believe less than half of the security candidates are competent in network security.
- 73% of new cyber security university graduates lack practical experience and knowledge related to the basics of cyber security.

Tan et al. (2018) also discussed possible career paths. To design and maintain a victorious cybersecurity program, you should strive to stimulate then address the labor needs. Previous studies on cybersecurity education have focused on two themes such as specialized labs, platforms, and technologies used in cybersecurity courses and offerings. One example is cybersecurity training courses and also textbooks. Several studies have concentrated on pedagogical approaches or models for developing cybersecurity courses (Abraham & Shih, 2015; Hetea et al., 2006; Yuan et al., 2017). Yuan et al. (2017) proposed the POGIL (Procedural Guided Learning) model. POGIL aims to improve non-technical skills for instances, attitude, inducement, and interest in education. It also proposes a comprehensive model of cybersecurity education is developed from its blended learning theory (Abraham & Shih, 2015).

Cybersecurity covers many topics but figuring out the cybersecurity issue to educate be able to difficult. Due to the time constraints of each semester, each degree program is responsible for defining and designing the topics and methods discussed in the discussion. The U.S. federal government has implemented various programs to develop higher education security policies, standards, and policies over the past two decades, such as National Telecommunications Security Policy. The NIST Cyber Security Frame, the National Initiative for strategic scheme for Education in Cyber Security (NICE, 2019), the National Education and Training Program in INFOSEC, and the National Conference on Education in Security of Information Systems are part of this work. This initiative focuses on training college and university students for information security roles. However, there has been no research focused on the theoretical foundations for developing cybersecurity courses based on the requirements of higher education institutions.

3.1.3 External entities deceive users into providing their personal information.

Cybersecurity issues in higher education can occur when entities outside the institution deceive users into disclosing their personal data. External entities are people or organizations with no primary role in an interaction or deal between two different parties but might be influenced or concerned about it. Most organizations use passwords to secure their systems against illegal entry. Improper access to systems, as well as data theft or system exploitation, is typically the result of criminals "cracking" user login credentials or obtaining them through hacking. Human factors need to be included in the conceptualization of protection processes because security is conceived, carried out, applied, and violated by humans. Human considerations are now more significant to hackers compared to cybersecurity professionals. Social manipulation approaches, such as fabrication and manipulation to get passwords, will take advantage of consumers who lack security understanding (Adams et al., 1999). They develop advertisements using open-source applications to ensure the person who clicks on them is human.

In general, educational institutions keep extensive data relating to their students, academic and non-academic employees. For example, residence locations, dates of birth, and complete names. Although this information might not appear as important as banking information and identification numbers, it can benefit cyber criminals. It enables phishing attacks that impersonate relatives or close friend members. Cybercriminals may also use this information to impersonate students or staff members for profit.

Lötter and Futcher (2014) state that email clients provide sufficient protection. Emails can also be a helpful tool for hackers planning phishing scams. The more genuine and reliable the email is, the more valuable it becomes in a security breach. By gaining access to an institution's email account, fraudsters may gain from a website's reliability to their phishing emails. The significant value of '.edu' email addresses belonging to students and faculty members is also frequently exposed publicly, making it easier for attackers to find and select targeted ones. Nonetheless, cybercriminals can quickly obtain an educational domain email address for themselves. For these factors, higher-education thefts start with an email assault. Higher education institutions, particularly their staff members, are more at risk of becoming a victim of phishing attempts. It is needed for only one staff person to make a mistake, and the threat may attack the whole university system.

3.2 Solution for the cyber security problems in higher education

3.2.1 *Improving the security system in higher education institutions*

Artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) have grown in popularity because of technological advances. This has resulted in an increase in cyber security threats in recent years (Eric CK Cheng and Tianchong Wang, 2022). The number of cyber-attacks has increased significantly as the Internet's interconnection has grown, and the nature of the attacks is changing (Eric CK Cheng and Tianchong Wang, 2022). As a result, corrective action should be taken to address this issue. Improving the security system in higher education institutions is one of the possible solutions to this problem. According to Mayieka Jared Maranga and Dr Masese Nelson, 2019 recommends that higher education institutions should invest in modern research laboratories and place a greater emphasis on individual and collective cyber security research and development. Higher institution also emphasizing that top management allocate appropriate financial resources to cyber security. Large allocations are required to provide related facilities and infrastructure, including obtaining the latest technology for use in higher education institutions to enable the digitization of security systems in national educational institutions. As a result, the government must play an important role in releasing the budget so that higher education institutions can further improve their security systems. Governments should think about implementing cyber security protection. Computers, networks, critical systems, software applications, and data in higher education institutions can all be protected from potential digital threats by using cyber security. Higher education institutions must maintain customer trust by implementing such cyber security safeguards.

Other than that, those in charge of the institution can also implement training and awareness programs aimed at increasing computer user awareness (Hussain Aldawood and Geoffrey Skinne, 2019). Cyber security awareness is critical for preventing society from becoming a victim of cybercrime. This awareness must be spread to all members of society. Students, on the other hand, are the group most vulnerable to cybercrime. This is because their age and level of thinking make them easy targets for cybercrime. As a result, school students must be educated on cybersecurity to avoid becoming victims of cybercrime. Because social engineering attacks are becoming more common, training and awareness programs have been developed (Hussain Aldawood and Geoffrey Skinne, 2019). Besides that, firewalls can be installed in educational institutions to improve cyber security. Firewalls and real-time protection antivirus programs have been developed as a response, according to (Eric CK Cheng and Tianchong Wang, 2022). Users can disable remote access from the computer with the proper firewall configuration and a modern operating system, preventing hackers from taking over the user's computer. By improving the cyber security system, higher education institutions can indirectly help to strengthen their cyber security systems from being compromised by irresponsible individuals.

3.2.2 *National Initiative for Cybersecurity Education (NICE) Strategic Plan.*

Users must be well-versed in recognizing and reacting to suspicious phishing emails before implementing technological alternatives. The research describes the critical aspects of a finished program for testing, training, measuring, and improving an entity's cybersecurity to address and minimize the possibility of phishing assaults. This program is based on practical experience in developing and carrying out training programs and working with National Institute of Standards and Technology guidelines. Increasing overall cyber security can lower the risk of phishing-based cyber-attacks.

As the demand for cyber security professionals grows, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) must launch Project NICE alongside the cyber security framework. The NICE Framework includes suggestions and directions for education professionals to establish training programs in cybersecurity that qualify graduates to fulfil the cybersecurity demand of higher education institutions. The framework lets lecturers develop a strict cybersecurity program that complies with the requirements of higher education institutions. (NICE Academic Spotlight, 2018).

In recent educational research, NICE has also been used to identify needs. For example, a recent study has used the NICE framework to pinpoint understanding, skills, and abilities to fulfil industrial cyber security requirements (Armstrong et al., 2020). The NICE framework serves as a critical reference for connecting cybersecurity education to the needs of higher education institutions. The NICE framework improves communication among cybersecurity educators, trainers, certifiers, employers, and employees. Second, primary analysis process highlights tasks that must be completed to function effectively in a specific work capacity. Third, skill analysis determines the position's job role and related tasks. Categories, areas of expertise, and job roles are all part of the NICE framework. The NICE framework's overall organizational components are provided by category. To fill industrial shortages, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) proposes the educational institutions match the courses of study with the NICE framework.

3.2.3 *Create an effective cyber risk management strategy*

Cyberattacks in higher education are common not because the IT infrastructures need to be more secure but because many institutions are vast, complicated, and use multiple systems programs and software. Users can connect to the internet via tablets or smartphones, making adopting safety measures harder. Higher education institutions use various cyber risk prevention techniques, including software and hardware upgrading to internet access management, traffic, and intrusion detection systems.

According to Liluashvili (2021), a proper cyber risk management plan is among the most critical aspects of an organization's cybersecurity. There are specific methods that institutions may employ to keep themselves protected when faced with the threat of risks associated with cyber security. To defend itself against cyberattacks, an entire organization must work together. Scholars and research institutes store vital research information that needs to be protected from cybercriminals. To preserve confidential data, researchers must work tactically with system authorities (Liluashvili, 2021). Higher educational institutions might develop collaborative teams comprised of heads of departments, researchers, and critical safety personnel. It is critical to remain cautious to guarantee that appropriate safety precautions are put in place to secure confidential private information and valuable research data. For effective operations of IT, those who use technology need to be allocated proper access credentials depending on the risk exposure.

According to Liluashvili (2021), a Privileged Access Management (PAM) solution is required to automate the administration of credentials and restricted access management. Another choice is to

regulate user access by staged access to administration, where the higher level allows more access to the needed but restricts access to limited users. Because hackers target administrator credentials to gain access to valuable data and acquire more influence in vulnerable systems, any particular account must be regularly watched. Having protocols for securely resetting identities like passwords, tokens, and tickers is critical. To preserve an appropriate level of cybersecurity for any organization, it is vital to compartmentalize user credentials and login access to certain employees. Due to the dangerous actor's restricted access features, the impact will be minor if a single section is hacked. There are fewer incidents of system blackouts at educational institutions that use the system.

Managing passwords is also essential for data security. Strong passwords are critical for securing business and personal information and maintaining privacy. Password policies were crucial for both regular and remote users. There are several guidelines that users need to comply with when trying to establish a password that might enhance security (Vu et al., 2007). One of the guidelines is that there must be a particular length requirement. Passwords must be at least eight characters in length. The more complicated the password, the more unlikely it is to be broken. Furthermore, users must refrain from employing basic patterns. Users need to avoid using uppercase letters at the start of a password or unusual symbols and digits at the end. Simple motifs can help with password remembering. However, they also make the password simpler to guess.

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the first issue mentioned above, having a weak security system policy can have an impact on cyber security. According to the evidence presented above, the party in charge of managing the system in higher education institutions does not update the software, and the operating system is the most vulnerable. This is because if the responsible party is not sensitive to the responsibility held, many parties will accept the consequences. This is because systems that have not been updated in a long time are more vulnerable to virus threats than devices that are serviced and updated regularly. To improve cyber security, responsible parties may consider installing firewalls in educational institutions. Some cyber threats can be blocked indirectly using a firewall. Furthermore, vendors frequently place and introduce unsafe products into the market, posing a risk. Products that are unsafe and of poor quality are frequently sold at lower prices. This will draw the attention of unscrupulous higher education institutions looking to cut costs. This is one of the primary causes of ineffective security systems. As a result, the government must play an important role in allocating additional funds so that higher education institutions can improve their security systems. Institutions with a larger budget can find higher-quality products. Furthermore, untrained workers and staff contribute to direct access attacks in large organizations, including connections to schools and universities. Untrained workers frequently make mistakes. Such errors can exacerbate cyber threats. Untrained employees are also more likely to be targeted by hackers. As a result, the party in charge of the institution can also implement training and awareness programs aimed at increasing computer users' awareness. The existence of such a program will indirectly open the eyes of the staff to a more responsible attitude toward user data. Employees will make greater efforts to learn how to use the system correctly and to prioritize safety. Finally, a lack of top management support contributes to the vulnerability of cyber systems. If the higher authorities refuse to release more funds to strengthen the system, the higher education institution will face numerous challenges. Superiors must be aware of their responsibility to strengthen their higher institutions' security systems to prevent information leakage. As a result, higher-level officials should invest in modern research labs and place a greater emphasis on individual and collective cybersecurity research and development. This is due to. A strong security system is necessary to ensure that higher education institutions' security levels are more stable.

According to Information Systems Education Research, IS courses must be formed to comply with the current needs of industries and businesses to train IS graduates for their future careers. This effort includes the Cybersecurity Framework developed by NIST, Role-Based Cybersecurity Training

Framework, National Initiative on Cybersecurity Education Strategic Plan (NICE, 2019), National INFOSEC Education and Training Program, and National Conference on Information Systems Security Education. However, no previous study has emphasized the conceptual framework to establish a cybersecurity program that meets the industry's requirements. The research's significant finding was the significance of creating a complete phishing education program in addition to email protection technologies. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) developed Project NICE alongside the cybersecurity framework to satisfy the increased request for cybersecurity specialists. The project's framework offers recommendations and guidelines for professionals in education to build cybersecurity training programs that prepare graduates to fulfil the industry's cybersecurity demands. The framework offers lecturers to create a strict cybersecurity program that meets the demands of the marketplace (NICE Academic Spotlight, 2018). For example, utilizing the NICE framework, a recent study has highlighted understanding, skills, and abilities to address industrial needs in cyber security (Armstrong et al., 2020). As main guidance, the framework significantly connects cybersecurity training with industrial demands in various ways. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) suggests educational institutions match the programs with the NICE framework to fill industrial gaps.

Cyber-attacks are becoming more common across every sector. The increasing focus on assaults on government institutions and important infrastructure has heightened interest in cybersecurity measures and laws. Higher education networks necessitate a complicated blend of convenient accessibility and very efficient safety measures. Because higher education institutes keep private and sensitive information of students and employees, they have become a popular aim for hackers seeking for the purpose of stealing data stored by these institutions. Furthermore, most colleges are becoming more forthcoming and open about their infrastructures. These educational institutions ensure that students and parents may access their sites fast and efficiently. This unintentionally opened the way for cybercriminals. Email phishing is a simple approach for cybercriminals to get access to university or college systems. Scholars and workers at higher education institutions can easily accept and finally fall for this hacker's fraud if just a trustworthy domain name such as '.edu' or '.org' is used. This security problem can be reduced by implementing a Privileged Access Management (PAM) system. This is because PAM software can allow safe distant access without requiring outsiders to supply domain identification, restricting access to necessary sources, and lowering the probability of illegal access to sensitive information. It can also guarantee that all external activities are tracked and documented.

5. CONCLUSION

Cybersecurity is no longer a hidden issue that only hackers are aware of. Higher education institutions have become more vulnerable to the problem as internet usage has increased. Due to a lax management environment, many higher education institutions are vulnerable to cyber-attacks. Based on our observations, hackers can exploit flaws in the defense system to steal data from any individual involved in a higher education institution, whether they are students, instructors, or staff. All higher education institutions that are transitioning from paper-based data should pay close attention to and prioritize cybersecurity when storing, accessing, and retrieving critical information. In this era, protecting information and data is a requirement for most higher education institutions around the world because data is an asset that can become problematic later if it falls into the hands of unauthorized individuals. Although cybercrime cannot be completely eradicated, higher education institutions must remain vigilant when using the internet to ensure that all online transactions are completed safely and without any data leakage. Therefore, higher education institutions must work together to maintain constant focus and attention to ensure information security, as well as implement appropriate security controls to prevent information leakage.

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